

Temporary Working Group (TWG)

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

Community-Standards for modelling fuzziness & wobbliness in research data using Semantic Web technologies and formalisms (FuzzyWobblySW)

Chairs: Florian Thiery (LEIZA); Karsten Tolle (Goethe-Universität Frankfurt am Main)

NFDI4Objects-Bodies Involved: LEIZA, Universität Frankfurt, TA2, TA4, TA6

External Connection: CAA Deutschland, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory, CIDOC-CRM SIG

Mailing List: n4o_twg_fuzzy-wobbly-sw@listserv.dfn.de [[subscribe](#)]

Steering Committee Resolution: 14.02.2025

Topics and Objectives

Exact and interpretative statements play a central role in exploring objects. The authors' "hidden assumptions," incomplete object preservation, or imprecise technical concepts can significantly influence the latter. Standardising the modelling of the associated "fuzziness and wobbliness" (e.g., uncertainty, vagueness, accuracy, and precision) in research data is challenging as different approaches are developed or implemented across research domains. The first step is defining "fuzziness and wobbliness" (Whitepaper #1).

The TWG aims to collect, evaluate, and enhance existing graph-based (RDF) modelling approaches (Whitepaper #2), software, and scripts (Whitepaper #3) for addressing "fuzziness and wobbliness" in research data. This will aid in identifying common interfaces that facilitate the transition from one domain-specific or research discipline-specific modelling approach to another.

This TWG will compile mathematical, information-technical, and other relevant implications of existing modelling approaches and implement prototypical approaches in use cases. This will enable researchers and students to assess the advantages and disadvantages verifiably.

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Out of Scope

This TWG concentrates exclusively on modelling approaches, such as RDF, to tackle fuzziness and wobbliness in semantic graph data. Other modelling concepts are referenced in Whitepaper #1 as conceptual considerations but are not elaborated upon in Whitepaper #2. Whitepaper #3 is dedicated entirely to the compilation of software and scripts related to graph data.

Integration

This TWG is actively involved in TRAILS 2.2 and 4.2 and in the work programme of Task Area 2, titled "Collecting."

Envisaged Commons Contributions

- **#1 Whitepaper:** *Definition of Fuzziness and Wobbliness*
- **#2 Whitepaper:** *Collection of Fuzziness and Wobbliness modelling Use-Cases on Semantic Web technologies and formalisms*
- **#3 Whitepaper:** *Collection of Software and Scripts on Fuzzyness und Wobbliness*
- **#4 Whitepaper:** *Evaluation of fuzzy & wobbly semantic alignment properties between authority files & community-driven vocabularies*
- **#1 Blueprint:** *Fuzzyness and Wobbliness Entity-Mapping-Ontology (CIDOC CRM & SKOS) for integration into the N4O OO and the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph*

Openness and Transparency

The TWG has the freedom to choose its communication methods and to coordinate and organise its meetings. Summary minutes of the meetings must be published. While there are no restrictions on the frequency of meetings, at least one meeting every three months is recommended to ensure ongoing activity. The public is invited to follow the work of the TWG and to participate in the discussions as part of the NFDI4Objects Commons processes. The TWG will make its results available for public reuse under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Metadata

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DC.contributor	Eide, Øyvind; Mees, Allard W.; Gampe; Sebastian et al.
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